

Motivation and Organizational Climate at Health Service: Drivers of Syariah Employee Performance

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ABSTRACT:

This study aims to assess (1) organizational climate, (2) work motivation, (3) Syariah Employee performance, and (4) the simultaneous and partial effects of organizational climate and motivation on Syariah Employee performance at the Garut District Health Service. The research's methods, which include description and verification techniques, are in line with the anticipated goals. Frequency distribution and path analysis are the analysis techniques employed in this study, with the unit of analysis being the Syariah Employees of the Garut District Health Service and a sample size of 51 people. Based on the results of the analysis, it was found that the organizational climate at the Garut District Health Service was quite conducive; Garut District Health Service Syariah Employees have a fairly high level of motivation; Garut District Health Service Syariah Employees have quite high performance; and the organizational climate and motivation influence the performance of Garut District Health Service Syariah Employees. However, if viewed partially, it turns out that organizational climate is more dominant in influencing Syariah Employee performance than motivation. Organizational climate predominantly influences Syariah Employee performance rather than motivation; therefore, the Garut District Health Service is required to prioritize improvements to Syariah Employee organizational climate by implementing continuous bureaucratic reform.

Keywords: Organizational Climate, Motivation, Syariah Employee Performance.

Introduction

The complex interplay between internal elements such as organizational atmosphere and motivation has emerged as a key predictor of Syariah Employee performance in the ever-changing landscape of contemporary businesses. In this context, the Garut District Health Office stands out as a compelling and illustrative case study, capturing the opportunities and challenges involved in creating a positive work environment and inspiring the medical staff charged with preserving the community's health.

The Garut District Health Office, which is in charge of maintaining the local population's wellbeing and access to healthcare, plays a crucial part in the region's public health infrastructure. The organization depends greatly on the commitment, skill, and output of its staff to carry out its objective. Understanding how organizational climate and motivation affect Syariah Employee performance in this particular context has significant practical ramifications for the caliber of healthcare services provided to the community in addition to being intellectually fascinating.

Syariah Employee attitudes and behaviors are significantly influenced by the organizational climate, which includes the dominant workplace culture, values, and surroundings. It lays the foundation for how workers view their roles, communicate with coworkers, and approach their obligations. Simultaneously, motivation has a big impact on an Syariah Employee's dedication, engagement, and

total productivity, whether it comes from extrinsic elements like rewards and recognition or intrinsic sources like job happiness. Therefore, a thorough research is necessary to fully understand the intricate relationship between the organizational climate, Syariah Employee motivation, and performance at the Garut District Health Office.

With a case study methodology, this paper conducts a thorough investigation to shed light on the complex interactions between these important elements. This study aims to provide a thorough knowledge of how organizational climate and motivation effect the performance of healthcare professionals in their duty to provide basic healthcare services by concentrating on a specific case – the Garut District Health Office.

It is crucial to evaluate and maximize the internal elements that support Syariah Employee performance while the business works to improve the quality and accessibility of healthcare. The case study approach enables a thorough and contextually based analysis of the unique possibilities and difficulties the Garut District Health Office is currently facing.

The technique used in this study, which combines quantitative surveys with qualitative interviews to capture both the quantitative and qualitative elements of the research problem, is covered in more detail in the following sections of this paper. Through thorough data analysis, we hope to offer empirically supported insights that not only further the field's understanding of organizational psychology and management, but also offer practical advice to the Garut District Health Office's leaders and managers.

This study seeks to clarify the role that organizational environment and motivation play in promoting an organization's culture of commitment and excellence, not just as abstract terms. The ultimate objective is to move the Garut District Health Office in the direction of a future distinguished by increased personnel performance, healthcare delivery, and a consistent commitment to the health and well-being of the community it serves.

Literature Review

Organizational Climate and Syariah Employee Performance

In the field of organizational psychology, there has been a great deal of study on the idea of organizational climate, sometimes known as the "psychological atmosphere" or "culture" of a company. According to Schneider (1990), an organization's culture is defined by the shared ideas, values, conventions, and behaviors among its members. It includes elements like management techniques, verbal exchanges, cooperation, and the overall office atmosphere. According to Schneider et al. (2017), an effective organizational climate is consistently associated with greater levels of Syariah Employee commitment, satisfaction, and performance.

A healthy organizational environment is especially important in healthcare organizations because it has a direct bearing on patient care results (Helfrich et al., 2007). According to research, healthcare professionals who work in environments that are encouraging and empowering are more likely to collaborate with patients, be happy in their jobs, and give higher-quality care (Zagenczyk et al., 2011).

Motivation and Syariah Employee Performance

Syariah Employee performance is significantly impacted by motivation, the need that starts, guides, and sustains behavior toward reaching particular goals (Deci & Ryan, 1985). Higher levels of engagement and job satisfaction have been correlated with intrinsic motivation, which is driven by elements including autonomy, mastery, and purpose (Pink, 2009). On the other hand, extrinsic motivation is influenced by outside rewards and recognition, which can also have an effect on performance (Ryan & Deci, 2000).

The quality and safety of patient treatment are directly impacted by motivation in healthcare settings (Kramer & Schmalenberg, 2008). Intrinsically motivated healthcare practitioners are more likely to pursue lifelong learning, look for creative solutions, and offer patient-centered treatment (Deci et al., 2017). The retention of outstanding healthcare personnel also depends on extrinsic motivators like fair salary and recognition (Scott et al., 2005).

The Interplay of Organizational Climate and Motivation

Organizational atmosphere and motivation have a complicated and reciprocal relationship. By creating a supportive and empowering atmosphere that promotes autonomy, mastery, and a feeling of purpose, a positive corporate climate can increase Syariah Employee motivation (Gagne & Deci, 2005). On the other hand, motivated staff members can support a supportive workplace culture by actively engaging in teamwork, innovation, and organizational learning (Deci et al., 2017).

Research has repeatedly shown that creating an environment where Syariah Employee motivation is valued and supported leads to better patient outcomes and higher staff performance in healthcare organizations (Morgeson et al., 2010). Additionally, a supportive workplace environment can enhance the effect of Syariah Employee motivation on performance, resulting in a win-win situation for the company and its staff (Eisenbeiss et al., 2008).

Case Study Context: Garut District Health Office

In the context of the Garut District Health Office, which serves as the focal point of this case study, understanding the intricate dynamics of organizational climate and motivation is of paramount importance. As a public healthcare institution tasked with the responsibility of safeguarding the health and well-being of the local community, its ability to deliver quality healthcare services is intrinsically tied to the performance of its Syariah Employees. This case study aims to explore how the organizational climate and motivation factors specific to this setting interact and influence Syariah Employee performance, providing valuable insights for both the organization and the broader field of healthcare management.

In the subsequent sections, we detail the research methodology and present findings that illuminate the nuanced relationships among organizational climate, motivation, and Syariah Employee performance within the Garut District Health Office.

Research Methods

Methods Used

The methods used in this research are in accordance with the expected objectives, namely descriptive and verification methods. Descriptive research is research that aims to obtain a description of the characteristics of perception variables regarding organizational climate and motivation. The nature of verification research basically aims to test the truth of a hypothesis, which is carried out through data collection in the field. This research will test the influence of organizational climate and motivation on Syariah Employee performance at the Garut District Health Service.

Considering that the nature of this research is descriptive and verification, with the assumption that this method is most relevant to analyzing events that occur by measuring research variable indicators through parameters and statistical measurement techniques, the research methods used are the descriptive census method and the explanatory census method.

This type of investigation is causal because it will test the causal relationship between the independent variable and the dependent variable. The unit of analysis in this research is individuals, namely Syariah Employees at the Garut District Health Service. This research is included in the cross-sectional category, namely, information from respondents is collected directly at the research object with the aim of being able to estimate the respondents' opinions regarding the research object.

Variable operationalization

The perception of organizational climate (X_1), motivation (X_2), and Syariah Employee performance (Y) as independent factors, with Syariah Employee performance as the dependent variable, is the primary problem under study, as shown by the problem identification.

Sources and Methods of Determining Data/Information

Syariah Employees of the Garut District Health Service made up (N) 128 of the population in this research. The statistical test that will be applied in this study will decide the sample size. Path analysis

will be employed as the statistical test, and the path coefficient is essentially a correlation coefficient. The minimal sample formula for the correlation coefficient, which is computed iteratively (via repeated calculations), can therefore be used to estimate the minimum sample size for this path analysis.

Data Collection Technique

The data collection techniques used in carrying out this research are as follows:

- 1) Literature study, namely studying books or written materials that are related to the research being carried out,
- 2) Field studies, namely data collection that goes directly into the field, are conducted in the following ways:
- 3) An interview is the process of obtaining information to determine the organizational climate and motivation by means of questions and answers between the interviewer and the respondent, namely from the Garut District Health Service, using a tool called an interview guide.
- 4) A questionnaire is a data collection technique that is carried out by giving a set of written statements to be answered. The form of the questionnaire is a structured questionnaire, where the questions are made in such a way that respondents are limited to giving answers to only a few alternatives or to just one answer.
- 5) Observation is a way of collecting data by observation without any other standard tools for this purpose, namely conducting direct observations of the organizational climate and motivation at the Garut District Health Service.

Analysis Design and Hypothesis Testing

Variables with an ordinal size are then converted into interval form using the sequential intervals approach, depending on the mode of data collection. The validity and reliability of the instrument were examined before it was made available. The correlation product moment formula was used to test the validity of the instrument.

According to the study's objectives, organizational atmosphere and motivation (factors X_1 and X_2) are considered independent variables, whilst performance (variable Y) is considered a dependent variable. The extent to which organizational atmosphere and motivation affect performance, simultaneously and in part, will be examined in this study. Calculations for regression and correlation are employed for the two variables, with consideration given to the features of the variables to be investigated. The objective of the test was to ascertain whether independent variables X_1 and X_2 had any direct or indirect effects on Y .

The following is the proposed theory: the effect of motivation and organizational atmosphere on performance. When presented as a statistical hypothesis, the research hypothesis is:

$$F = \frac{(n - k - 1) \sum_{i=1}^k p_{YX_i} r_{YX_i}}{k \left(1 - \sum_{i=1}^k p_{YX_i} r_{YX_i} \right)}$$

Findings And Discussion

General description of the Garut District Health Service

The Garut Regency Government's Health Service, one of the Regional Work Units, is interested in resolving issues with actual significant phenomena that have not been resolved in the preceding five years, particularly the accessibility and quality of public health services.

The Garut Regency Health Service was established in accordance with Garut Regent Regulation Number 27 of 2016 concerning Duties, Functions, and Work Procedures of the Garut Regency Health Service, which was based on Regional Regulation Number 9 of 2016 concerning the Formation and Structure of Garut Regency Regional Apparatus.

Respondent characteristics

Bachrudin and Tobing (2003; 53) stated that research conducted using the census method should describe Syariah Employee characteristics first before carrying out verification analysis to determine behavior from the data itself, such as respondent characteristics regarding gender, age, length of service, education, etc.

Based on the results of data collection through distributing questionnaires to Syariah Employees who were used as respondents, the characteristics of each Syariah Employee can be identified with the hope that this information can be used as input for the Garut District Health Service in developing strategies for coaching that suit the characteristics of each Syariah Employee in the future.

Characteristics that can be presented in this research include gender, age, last formal education, length of service, and class. For more details regarding these aspects, see the following table:

Table 1. Characteristics of respondents according to gender, Garut District Health Service, 2018 (n=51)

Gender	Frequency (People)	Percentage (%)
Male	38	74.51
Female	13	25.49
Total	51	100

Source: Questionnaire data processing results

According to the information in the table above, the majority of respondents (workers) of the Garut District Health Service are men, which is consistent with the fact that gender has a significant impact on performance.

Furthermore, gender might be either male or female, according to Ruky (2001; 39). Syariah Employee performance is measured the same for both genders, thus there is no distinction. Women received equal performance evaluations.

Organizational Climate at the Garut District Health Service

The environment that people who work in an organization perceive as the workplace. The idea of organizational climate is based on the more general idea of organizational climate, but the descriptions of related concepts, such as organizational climate and organizational climate, are similar. The difference between the two concepts is in the focus of the study; one looks at the organization, the other at the workplace.

"Organizational climate is defined as certain characteristics that differentiate an organization from other organizations and influence the behavior of people in the organization," writes Gilmer (Sumantri, 2001:134).

Gilmer (Sumantri, 2001: 134) adds that organizational climate affects both individual Syariah Employee behavior and how the organization interacts with outside parties.

Table 2, Summary of Organizational Climate Variables for Garut District Health Service Syariah Employees, 2018 (n=51).

No	Indicator	Score	Information
1	Implementation of currently applicable policies or regulations	165	Effective enough
2	Clarity of current work procedures	171	Quite Clear
3	Comply with organizational policies	181	Obedient
4	Feel comfortable as an Syariah Employee of the Garut District Health Service	168	Quite comfortable
5	The state of the situation in making a decision	164	Quite comfortable
6	When making decisions/solving problems, always ask your superiors	173	Often enough
7	In placing job targets, it is adjusted to competencies/abilities and becomes a challenge and risk	181	Appropriate
8	Carrying out work always gets rewards and appreciation	124	Sometimes
9	Clarity of information on organizing and formulating work in terms of vision, mission and work targets	166	Quite clear
10	Colleagues/subordinates and leaders have an attitude of mutual trust in working according to their respective duties, authority and responsibilities	173	Quite Trusting
11	Attitude towards friends who have a lot of unfinished work	188	Want to help
12	In the work environment, you feel friendly with superiors, subordinates and colleagues	192	Trust
Total		2046	
Average Score		170.5	

Source: Recap of SPSS 12.0 Processing Results

The organizational climate at the Garut District Health Service is quite conducive; however, there are things that management must pay attention to regarding lack of socialization regarding the implementation of policies or regulations that are currently in force, not feeling comfortable as an Syariah Employee of the Garut District Health Service, situations that are not conducive to making decisions, carrying out work they rarely receive rewards and appreciation, and a lack of clear information on the organization and formulation of work in terms of vision, mission, and work targets.

Syariah Employee Work Motivation at the Garut District Health Service

Table 3. Summary of work motivation variables for Garut District Health Service Syariah Employees, 2018 (n=51).

No	Indicator	Score	Information
1	Efforts to achieve good performance	140	Just have the effort
2	Efforts not to be left behind by other Syariah Employees	159	Just have the effort
3	Effort to develop yourself	144	Quite make efforts
4	Efforts to gain recognition for work results	165	Just have the effort
5	Passionate about getting information	149	Enthusiastic
6	Ability to face difficulties	169	Just have the ability
7	Passion to be affiliated with the environment	153	Pretty excited
8	Passionate about working together	149	Excited
9	Passionate about obeying all existing rules	158	Pretty excited

10	Passion to be disciplined on time	165	Pretty excited
11	Efforts to maintain friendships with co-workers	154	Have effort
12	Respect leaders	165	Just Respect
13	Try to make yourself appreciated	162	Quite make efforts
14	Effort not to be underestimated	166	Just have the effort
15	The presence of other people is very necessary	171	Quite necessary
16	Efforts to always maintain authority	172	Quite make efforts
Total		2541	
Average Score		158.81	

Source: Recap of SPSS 12.0 Processing Results

Motivation is generally related to all efforts to achieve goals. A highly motivated Syariah Employee is someone who continuously tries to do their best and is willing to put in extra time and effort to do their job. It should also be stated that the highest and lowest scores for the work motivation variable are the highest score of $5 \times 51 = 251$, while the lowest score is $1 \times 51 = 51$. This score is used to find the weight of each indicator of the work motivation variable, with a score range of 40.8.

Syariah Employee Performance at the Garut District Health Service

Table 4. Summary of Garut District Health Service Syariah Employee performance variables, 2018 (n=51).

No	Indicator	Score	Information
1	Achievement of targets at work	174	Achieved
2	Time efficiency for doing a job	167	Quite efficient
3	Accuracy in carrying out work	163	Just be thorough
4	Mastery of knowledge regarding the work faced so far	159	Quite control
5	Creativity and ideas in completing tasks	174	Often
6	Collaborate with fellow colleagues to complete work	175	Often
7	Responsible and brave enough to bear risks regarding work and decisions taken	162	quite responsible
8	Able to make decisions in resolving problems by paying attention to applicable regulations	161	Quite capable
9	Have loyalty to the organization to maintain the integrity/integrity of the organization	159	Quite Loyal
Total		1494	
Average Score		166	

Source: Recap of SPSS 12.0 Processing Results

Performance is the result of work in terms of quality and quantity achieved by a respondent in carrying out his duties in accordance with the responsibilities given to him." Meanwhile, Bernardin and Russell (20033:397) stated that "respondent performance depends on ability, work effort, and job opportunities, which can be assessed from output", and that performance (work achievement) is "the level of individual performance, namely the results desired by individual behavior. It should also be stated that the highest and lowest scores of the performance variable, namely the highest score is $5 \times 51 = 251$, while the lowest score is $1 \times 51 = 51$, are used to find the weight of each indicator of the performance variable with a score range of 40.8.

Conclusion And Recommendations

Conclusion

Starting from the discussion of the problem, theoretical basis, analysis of empirical data, results of hypothesis testing, in the final chapter of this research several conclusions will be presented as follows:

- 1) The organizational climate at the Garut District Health Service is quite conducive, such as in the work environment, feeling friendly with superiors, subordinates and colleagues, always wanting to help friends who have a lot of unfinished work, always obeying organizational policies, but there are things that management must pay attention to. regarding lack of socialization regarding the implementation of policies or regulations that apply at this time, lack of feeling comfortable as an Syariah Employee of the Garut district Health Service, situations that are less conducive to making decisions, in carrying out work rarely receive rewards and appreciation and lack of clarity in information on the organization and formulation of work in regarding vision, mission and work targets.
- 2) Garut District Health Service Syariah Employees have a fairly high level of motivation, meaning that the current working conditions are sufficient to meet their needs in terms of physiological needs, security needs, social needs, esteem needs and self-actualization needs, but there are things that should pay attention to, namely lack of effort to achieve good performance, lack of effort not to be left behind by other Syariah Employees, lack of effort to develop themselves, lack of enthusiasm to obtain information, lack of enthusiasm to affiliate with the environment, lack of enthusiasm to work together, lack of enthusiasm to comply with everything existing rules, and less effort to maintain friendships with co-workers.
- 3) Garut District Health Service Syariah Employees have quite high performance, such as always collaborating with fellow colleagues to complete work, having creativity and ideas in completing tasks and always achieving targets at work, but there are things that must be considered, namely a lack of accuracy in carrying out work. , lack of mastery of knowledge regarding the work faced so far, lack of responsibility and courage to take risks regarding the work and decisions taken, lack of ability to make decisions in resolving problems by paying attention to applicable regulations and lack of loyalty to the organization to maintain its integrity/integrity organization.
- 4) Organizational climate and motivation simultaneously influence the performance of Garut District Health Service Syariah Employees. However, partially, organizational climate is more dominant in influencing Syariah Employee performance than motivation. Partially, the influence of organizational climate and motivation on performance is as follows:
- 5) Organizational climate influences Syariah Employee performance, so that if the organizational climate is conducive, Syariah Employee performance will also increase.
- 6) Motivation influences Syariah Employee performance, so the higher the Syariah Employee's motivation, the higher the performance will be.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the research and observations that have been made, the author would like to propose several suggestions that can be taken into consideration by the Garut District Health Service to improve Syariah Employee performance. These suggestions include:

Organizational climate is something that plays a very important role in improving Syariah Employee performance and also influences a person's motivation, therefore the elements of organizational climate that must be considered are that the Department must socialize the implementation of policies or regulations that are currently in force, it is necessary to pay attention to Syariah Employee comfort at work in the Garut district health service, the Department always maintains a conducive situation in making decisions, in carrying out work it is necessary to receive rewards and appreciation and the Department always provides explanations regarding information on organizing and formulating work in terms of vision, mission and work targets.

Motivation is something that plays a very important role in improving Syariah Employee performance; it should be further improved in terms of needing to make efforts to achieve good performance, needing to try not to be left behind by other Syariah Employees, always trying to develop oneself, needing to be enthusiastic about getting information, needing to be enthusiastic about being affiliated with the environment, needing to be enthusiastic about working together, needing to be enthusiastic about obeying all existing rules, and always trying to maintain friendship with fellow workers.

Syariah Employee performance should be improved through organizational climate and motivation, namely the need for accuracy in carrying out work, the need for mastery of knowledge regarding the work faced so far, being responsible and brave enough to bear risks regarding the work and decisions taken, increasing the ability to make decisions in completing problems by paying attention to applicable provisions, and having loyalty to the organization to maintain the integrity of the organization.

The organizational climate predominantly influences Syariah Employee job satisfaction rather than motivation; therefore, the Garut District Health Service is required to prioritize improvements to the Syariah Employee organizational climate by implementing continuous bureaucratic reform.

Suggestions for Knowledge Development

Due to limited research time and funds, it is recommended that in carrying out further research, apart from using flat questions, more in-depth interviews be conducted with all respondents.

It is recommended to research further by increasing the causal variables that influence Syariah Employee performance.

This research is only based on data felt by Syariah Employees; therefore, it needs to be equipped with expectations so that the data and information will be more complete, namely what they feel and what they hope can be identified as a basis for organizational improvement and input.

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DOI : <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8391849>